

FORMATION OF COMPACT AND EFFECTIVE PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

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ABSTRACT

In this article, by simplifying the management system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, optimizing the number of management bodies by introducing new administrative reforms in the system, eliminating functions that repeat each other, full service of citizens is justified. Also, in scientific work, together with foreign countries, the activities of competent authorities in the field of education, finance, anti-corruption are carried out and appropriate conclusions are given to eliminate problems.

On December 20, 2022, in his address to the Oliy Majlis and the people, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev proposed switching to a compact and efficient system of public administration.

A compact and efficient public administration system depends on several factors, the most important of which is the number and quality of public administration bodies.

Today in our country there are 25 ministries, 10 state committees, 3 state inspections, 16 agencies, 5 committees, 6 centers, 2 central institutions and 4 inspections. It can be seen that the total number of public administration bodies in our country is 71.

In addition, Uzbekistan also has a total of 62 economic management bodies in the form of associations, companies, associative associations, foundations and others.

There are also a total of 14 administrative-territorial units and 209 district (city) municipalities that are part of the public administration system. From this it can be seen that there are about 350 public administration bodies.

Let's analyze these public administration bodies in the context of certain areas. In the field of combating corruption. In order to regulate the anti-corruption sphere in the Republic of Uzbekistan and ensure its prevention and control, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" has been adopted. The law assigns control over the industry to 6 state governing bodies. They are determined by the Anti-Corruption Agency, the Prosecutor General's Office, the Department for Combating Economic Crimes under the Prosecutor General's Office, the State Security Service, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Justice. Based on the recommendations of the OECD regulatory policy, it is indicated that the regulation and improvement of one industry is entrusted to one governing body.

It is possible to see the presence of repetitive functions in the implementation of the activities of these bodies mentioned above.

In particular, he coordinates activities in the field of combating corruption, analyzes the implementation of legislative acts in this area, conducts information and analytical, organizational, methodological and control activities,

2. participation in the development and implementation of state programs in the field of anti-corruption,

3. considers appeals of individuals and legal entities on the facts of corruption and takes measures to restore their violated rights and protect their legitimate interests,

4. participates in activities aimed at raising legal awareness, legal culture and strengthening the rule of law in society among the population;

5. develops measures to ensure timely receipt, detection and termination of corruption offenses, to eliminate their consequences, as well as the causes and conditions that allow them, and the implementation of which is entrusted to all the above-mentioned bodies,

- it can also be seen that in accordance with article 345 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the investigation of criminal cases related to articles 205-215, mainly related to official and corruption crimes, was entrusted to the Prosecutor's Office, but according to the law it was also authorized by the National Security Service and the Ministry of Internal Affairs to conduct preliminary.

In addition, risk assessment in the current regulatory policy of the state, when determining the rules and documents contained in corruption elements, is also in accordance with the purpose of imposing it on one body of the state administration apparatus.

Looking at the experience of foreign countries in this regard, we can say that the fight against corruption is carried out by a single body. For example, in France, the only anti-corruption body is the National Anti-Corruption Center, in Turkey it is a subsidiary of the Ministry of Finance, and the US Treasury Department is the state anti-corruption body.

Proposals aimed at solving problems: for centralized regulation of this sphere by the state, it is necessary to clearly define the functions and goals of the established governing bodies, correctly distribute tasks among them, remove repetitive powers and assign them to one responsible body, connect unified interactive databases of all organizations to the anti-corruption body, assess risks, involve the private sector.

Ecology and environmental protection. In the Republic of Uzbekistan there are several authorized bodies regulating the sphere of ecology and environmental protection, which can be divided into general and specially authorized bodies. The general government bodies include the Cabinet of Ministers, local self-government bodies. Special bodies may include the State Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Forestry Committee, the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of Water Resources, the State Plant Quarantine Inspectorate under the Cabinet of Ministers, the Department for Supervision of the Implementation of Legislation on Nature Protection in the Prosecutor General's Office. As we can see by the example of foreign countries, in such developed countries as Japan, Germany, France, China, South Korea, the function of environmental protection Ecology and artof is carried out by the Ministry of Ecology and

Environmental Protection. This ensures the formation of a unified system, putting an end to the predominance of state bodies in this area.

The field of education. Today, this direction is represented by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of the Education Department under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic, the regulatory bodies are the state testing center under the Cabinet of Ministers and the Agency for the popularization of Foreign language learning under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Abroad, in most cases, it can be seen that the field of education is carried out by a single body. For example, in the United Arab Emirates, the Ministry of Education implements public policies related to preschool education, public education and higher education, including vocational, technical, private and continuing education, and prepares, implements and monitors relevant strategies and legislation. In Germany, the Federal Ministry of Education and Scientific Research of Germany can be referred to as the special and only competent authority at the federal level in the field of education. It is noteworthy that this ministry finances scientific projects and institutions, as well as regulates the general state policy in the field of education. Finland may also refer to the Ministry of Education and Culture of Finland as the special and only competent authority in the field of education. The Ministry of Education and Culture defines the main directions of primary, secondary, vocational and higher education of the country, it is also clear that art, scientific research, sports, youth and copyright protection are also included in the scope of functions of this ministry.

It seems that the proposal of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the transition to a compact and efficient system of public administration in his message to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan plays an important role and puts an end to the repetition of tasks and functions in state bodies, appeals about sansoism and irresponsibility. Ultimately, a compact and efficient management system is formed.

Today in the Republic of Uzbekistan there are several competent authorities regulating the financial sector, it is necessary to optimize these organizations, clarify their tasks and reduce tasks and functions that repeat each other. There are several other ministries and departments, such as the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction and the Mahallaboya Agency for Labor and Entrepreneurship Development, the State Tax Committee, the State Customs Committee, the State Reserves Management Committee under the Cabinet of Ministers, the State Statistical Committee, the Ministry of Investment and Foreign Trade. The analysis shows that the tasks and functions of these ministries and departments related to the regulation of the financial sector can be considered as repetitive and returning each other. The experience of foreign countries shows that the regulation of the aforementioned financial sector is carried out by one agency in foreign countries.

In particular, the only body regulating the financial sector at the federal level in Germany is the Ministry of Finance of the Federal Republic of Germany, which includes the Department of Economic Policy and Financial Market, the Departments of Customs and Tax

Policy, the U.S. Treasury Department in the United States, which includes the Inspector General of the Treasury for Tax Administration, the State Accounting Chamber and Department of State Assets Management of the Ministry of Finance, France's economy and Recovery are supported by the State Control, the Department of Macroeconomics and Economics, the Department of Foreign Economy and the Ministry of Trade.

Regulation and management of the financial sector by a single state body, coupled with an exceptionally positive impact on the quality of management of foreign countries, the experience of which is given above, is carried out by a single minister with the overall leadership of various departments, inspections, agencies, ensuring the reduction of unnecessary official state units, saving the state budget, ultimately.

Currently, in most of the state bodies of our country, the order of work is still being formed in the old-fashioned way. In particular, work with reports is still carried out in paper form, despite the transition to the exchange of electronic documents. Bureaucratic formalities are commonplace in the style of work of ministries and departments. In addition, the constant holding of meetings, gatherings, selectors leads to the fact that ministries and departments spend less time and resources to work within the framework of the main task, the functions assigned to them, duties. The main job remains participation in meetings.

Also, another negative aspect is the pursuit of figures, which are also included and added to the work that has not been done for reports, reference books. At the same time, the system of work in anticipation of the arrival of an order or instruction from above is one of the main shortcomings and current situations of our state bodies today, which has a negative impact on the development of society and the state. However, the functions, assignments and scope of responsibility of state bodies are determined by the relevant legislative norms.

At the same time, the main task of the French Ministry of Agriculture and Food is to develop and coordinate state policy in the field of agriculture, agri-food business, forestry and woodworking industry, fisheries and aquaculture. In close cooperation with the Ministry of Economy and Finance, the Ministry of Health and Solidarity, it develops and implements the State food policy. It also participates in the implementation of State policy in the field of international trade. On this issue, he expresses the opinion of the French Government in various organizations at the international level. No structure can give other tasks and orders to this ministry, and this ministry does not perform anything other than the tasks assigned to it.

In Germany, the work of the Federal Ministry of Economy and Combating Climate Change has become fundamentally modern, while at the same time emphasizing the preservation of ties with local and national traditions. In particular, the Ministry has identified as the main goal the development of naturally formed clusters between high-performance small, medium and large companies and research institutes. In addition, it was established that the company will take additional measures to support artificial intelligence and basic security technologies. The main goal is to fulfill the functions and tasks of the state body itself.

It follows from this that the working methods of ministries and organizations operating in Uzbekistan have reached an outdated level that does not meet the requirements of the time. Timely awareness of these circumstances and taking measures remains one of the most pressing issues today. The President also spoke about this in his address to the Oliy Majlis and

noted that, first of all, ministries will be reformed, and the style of their work will be radically changed.

And it is necessary that the change in the style of work begins first of all with the rejection of assembly, eye-catching, stopping the pursuit of numbers. It is obvious that organizations are engaged in strengthening the connection of their employees with citizens and practice, focusing on the development and effective implementation of rational proposals and ideas for solving practical problems.

It should be noted that civil servants working in the public sector today amount to 2,539,600 people, in addition to the data of the State Statistics Committee, which is 56,500 more than in 2020 (2,483,100). From year to year, there is an increase in budget expenditures as a result of an increase in the number of civil servants. In particular, according to the State Statistics Committee, the average monthly salary in 2020 will amount to 3,551,589 soums, excluding 2,673,284 soums and payments of 49,185,080,000 soums from the budget to an additional 56,500 public sector employees.

The reason is that we see that the number of employees working in the public sector in some foreign countries is compact and small. Including 87 thousand in Singapore, 3 million in Japan. It can be seen that 300 thousand civil servants work. Employees working in the public sector, in relation to the number of Axoli, make up 1.48 percent in Singapore (the number of axoli is 5,866,139), 2.6 percent in Japan (the number of axoli is 125,309,000), 2.6 percent in Uzbekistan (the number of axoli is 36 million) while it is 7.5 percent, and this in turn indicates that that we have a very large expansion of the state apparatus.

In his address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan dated December 20, 2022, it was proposed to switch to ihcham and an effective system of public administration, which, in turn, will gradually reduce the number of civil servants by 30-35% by optimizing the areas analyzed above and will open the way for the direction of economic funds to social issues.

In conclusion, an effective organization of public administration, by reducing repetitive tasks and functions of each other in public administration bodies, contributes to improving the efficiency of work and, ultimately, a full understanding of the obligations of each state body to our people.

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